

Dynamic analysis of global titanium trade

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Abstract: The markets of metals and chemical products are the most important areas of the world economy and production. In this work, titanium and titanium products were chosen as the object of research. In the course of the analysis, the economic indicators of the production and sale of titanium and products from it were determined and analysed, taken in dynamics. The research provides an overview of current trends in the global titanium trade during the post-pandemic recovery. The assessment of the development of the global titanium market is given. It is concluded that the particularly rapid growth of economic activity in titanium consumer industries was due to the desire of many countries to develop industrial enterprises. Clusters of the world's main trades of titanium-containing concentrates and titanium sponge have been identified. The range of factors potentially influencing the dynamics of the price of titanium sponge is investigated, the independence of this dynamics is shown from fluctuations in supply and demand, the price of raw materials. It is given a quantitative assessment of the degree of influence of titanium on the level of world trade. Moreover, it is concluded that stimulating economic programs of governments around the world play an extremely important role in the development of the titanium trade market.

Keywords: Global Economy, Dynamic Analysis, Titanium Trade Market, World Market.

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1. Introduction

Titanium is called the “third metal” and the “almighty metal” because of its excellent performance and wide range of applications. Titanium is one of the most widely distributed elements in the earth's crust, accounting for 0.61% of the mass of the earth's crust, ranking ninth. Due to the increasing use of titanium resources, it is second only to iron and aluminium and is known as the “third metal”.

Titanium concentrate is mainly used in the production of titanium dioxide, and part of it is used in the production of sponge titanium and other titanium products. Titanium concentrate is processed and produced as titanium dioxide. Titanium dioxide, as the highest quality white pigment in the world, is mainly used in the production of coatings, plastics, paper and ink; sponge titanium is processed into titanium and used in such high-class industrial areas as aerospace, construction, petrochemical, shipbuilding, medical and other military industries. Titanium is used in the aerospace industry for the manufacture of chassis, blades and turbine discs, in the marine industry titanium sheet is used for the manufacture of ships and submarines, and in the automotive industry it is used in components for internal combustion engines.

1.1 The expansion of associated industries drives the boom of titanium trade

Titanium-containing raw materials and titanium products are important materials for many industries, such as aerospace, construction, automotive and nuclear and energy. In recent years, these industries have demonstrated constant growth and rapid technological evolution. In this context, the prospects for the development of titanium-containing raw materials and titanium products remain high.

The expansion of construction activity in North America is expected to lead to the rapid growth of the titanium market in the coming years. It is expected that the growth of the construction, automotive and other related industries will contribute to an increase in the consumption and use of titanium and its products in Europe in the upcoming years. It is also worth noting that one of the main factors contributing to the growth of the titanium market is the growing demand for electric vehicles. This is due to rising fuel prices and environmental pollution problems caused by gasoline-powered cars. The need for titanium wire in Europe was caused by the using of titanium wire in the production of German pellets, automotive parts for companies such as BMW, Volkswagen and others, as well as in other production processes. The demand for finished titanium in Europe is largely determined by the automotive sector. In addition, another consumer of titanium in this area is the construction industry, and moreover, do not forget about medical equipment. Since many large, high-tech and well-known clinics are located in Europe, respectively, they are also consumers of titanium for the manufacture of medical equipment, light and durable surgical instruments, for the replacement of joints and dental implants.

The Asia-Pacific region retains its dominance in the titanium dioxide market. It can be explained by the construction activity growth in India, China and other Southeast Asian countries, as a result of which the demand for paint and varnish materials is increasing. In turn, it leads to the increasing in demand for products and stimulates further growth of the titanium dioxide market. The expansion of the market is also due to the rapid industrialization and economic development in the region. In addition, the growing titanium demand in the end-use sectors, such as paints, paper, plastics, cellulose, printing inks, paints, chemical fibers and others, is one of the main factors in this market growth. The titanium pigment market is expected to expand due to technological advances aimed at optimizing production technologies for increasing production quantity and improve its quality.

1.2 New uses for titanium dioxide also stimulate the trade of titanium

In addition to the fact that the global titanium dioxide market is rapidly developing, which is primarily characterized by the possibility of widespread use of titanium dioxide in various industries, new uses for titanium dioxide are being developed, building a foundation for its future production, thanks to an increasing number of patents and research projects.

The demand for titanium dioxide as a coating material is rising in response to the increased need for highly scratch-resistant materials. The development of the titanium industry was also driven by the global demand for jewelry, due to the numerous distinctive qualities of this metal. Thus, the titanium industry market is constantly developing. The growth of titanium consumption in various industries, such as aviation, space, medical, as well as in the mobile and cosmetic industries, create a need to increase its extraction, processing and production. Moreover, the demand for titanium and its alloys continues to grow, and the forecasts for the titanium market for the coming years remain stable, as the demand for aircraft and more efficient transportation also continues to grow. In addition, titanium and its products create new opportunities for the development of high-tech mechanisms, products, facilities and the aerospace sector, thereby allowing countries to increase the innovation and technology level, which contributes to the strengthening and development of their economics.

1.3 Objectives and structure

The main issues and problems investigated in this paper on the topic of world trade of titanium and titanium products are:

- price dynamics of titanium and titanium concentrates;

- the influence of supply and demand factors on the dynamics of prices for titanium sponge and titanium rolled products;
- current state, problems, prospects of development of the titanium trade market in the world;
- effects of coronavirus infection on the titanium trade.

The object of research of this work is the global industrial metal market, where the subject of research is global trade of titanium.

For a detailed and logically based dynamic analysis of the global titanium trade market, I have divided my research into several key points. First of all, the specialization of the titanium industry was determined, with specific functions and tasks of titanium raw materials.

Next, the titanium market was considered, which consists of the titanium dioxide market, the titanium metal market, titanium ores and concentrates, titanium waste and scrap, ferro-titanium and ferro-silico-titanium. Based on the data on the titanium market divisions, the following aspects were analysed in detail: world trade volumes, trade structure, the leading trading countries in the world market, the impact of the Covid-19 on the target segment of the titanium market. In order to determine the current state of the titanium industry market, the leading countries in the production of titanium dioxide, sponge titanium and so on were identified, an analysis of titanium and titanium-containing concentrates imports and exports and price dynamics was carried out. Since global production and the global economy are interconnected with political and social problems, respectively, events such as Covid-19 economic crises have played a huge role in the target segment of the titanium market. These data were also used to determine the main trade prospects, challenges and threats of the development of titanium-containing raw materials and titanium products.

Recommendations to cope with the challenges of the titanium trade was made, as well as a conclusion, based on the entire research.

2. Literature Review

Not many researches have been conducted in the field of titanium, but I have used the most valuable and interesting ones in my work. Articles from Maximize Market Research titled "Titanium Market: Global Industry Analysis and Forecast (2022-2029)", "Titanium Dioxide Market Size, Share & Trends [2023 Report]" from Grand View Research, as well as an article "Modeling of Titanium Metal Market Trends" from Mineral Sands Industry Information, Iluka Sands became very useful for analyzing the global titanium and titanium products market. To analyze the titanium market by producing and consuming countries, as well as to understand the market dynamics, published data and research studies from the US Geological Survey were included, where the author Joseph Gambogi provided detailed information on the production and supply of titanium sponge, titanium dioxide, titanium concentrates, and so on by year and by country. In addition, the information provided by Trade Map was used for the basic analysis of imports, exports, price dynamics and the impact of Covid-19. The works of Russian scientists have made a great contribution to my research. For example, a scientific article by A.V. Sokolov titled "Modeling of Titanium Metal Market Trends", where the author investigated the dynamics of world production of titanium sponge, the factors influencing the dynamics of the titanium sponge price, showed the independence of this dynamics from fluctuations in supply and demand, the raw materials price. In addition, the scientific article "The Current State of the Titanium-Containing Raw Materials Market in the World and Russia" written by Yu. A. Arkhipova explained the structure of titanium consumption in the world. These studies confirm the need for titanium production, as well as provide unique information and data. As for predicting the future development of titanium and its products, as well as the difficulties that manufacturing countries and the entire titanium industry in general may face. Titanium trading is a complex and quite expensive business area, requiring large initial and monthly capital investments, but based on statistics, published articles also show that titanium production has potential benefits for many countries.

For many industries, such as aerospace, nuclear, automotive and energy, and also that the widespread use of titanium and titanium products have a great influence on the international market of goods and services and on the scientific and technological development of countries.

3. Global titanium trade review

The titanium market is complex, multi-stage, and, most importantly, closed, which complicates the search for information and data. It should be noted that titanium belongs to the group of strategic materials, the availability of which fully determines the ability to produce high-tech and competitive products in terms of their characteristics. That is why it is possible to characterize the market of titanium, titanium concentrates and titanium alloys as highly competitive. This global titanium trade review examines the import, export and price dynamics of titanium and its products, divided by titanium market segments, producing and consumer countries. Moreover, the total trade growth, trade distribution, including all the countries were determined. The market review contains an analysis of the impact of Covid-19 on the entire titanium market.

The data was taken from the Trade Map website and used for its own calculations. Figures, graphs and tables are used to analyze key data for the historical period from 2003 to 2022, but many data for 2022 were hidden from public use. Accordingly, I was forced to use data up to and including 2021 in some tables.

3.1 Titanium Import

3.1.1 Top 5 imports countries are USA, Germany, France, China and UK

The top 5 import countries import over 70% of the global titanium. According to the Observatory of Economic Complexity (OEC), “in 2021 the top importers of Titanium were United States, Germany, France, China, and United Kingdom” (view in the Figure 1). “Between 2020 and 2021, the fastest growing importers of Titanium were China (\$109M), Switzerland (\$31.4M), India (\$24.9M), Chinese Taipei (\$23M), and Ukraine (\$14.1M)”.

Fig. 1: Importers of titanium (2021) in millions of US Dollars

Source: Observatory of Economic Complexity (OEC), 2021

Accordingly, 12.9% of titanium is imported by America, 10.6% by Germany, 10.1% by France, 9.5% by China, 7.3% by United Kingdom (Figure 2).

Fig. 2: Importers of titanium (2021) by percentage%

Source: calculated by me based on information: Observatory of Economic Complexity (OEC), 2021

3.1.2 Different categories of the titanium’s import fluctuate differently

Figure 3 shows the dynamics of the global titanium import from 2003 to 2021. The initial data for calculations are Trade Map data on the world value of titanium and its products imports from 2003 to 2021. The data are presented as a percentage of the level of the base year 2003 and calculated by me. As can be seen from the data shown in Figure 3, the titanium market is divided into five main segments such as Titanium oxides, Titanium ores and concentrates, Titanium waste and scrap, Pigments and preparations based on TiO₂, Ferro-titanium and ferro-silico-titanium.

Titanium oxides and pigments imports tend to develop more steadily. As for the other three market segments, they have a rather abrupt nature of development. For example, the import of ferro-titanium and ferro-silico-titanium in 2005 reached its peak with a rather sharp jump. The same pattern can be traced with the titanium ores and concentrates market in 2012, in the same year titanium oxides import also increased, but the jump was not as sharp as concentrates. As for titanium waste and scrap, imports are not quite stable, there was a noticeable decline in 2009, after that the percentage of waste and scrap imports is more or less stabilized. In addition, the general pattern of all market segments is that the percentage of all imported products fell in 2020 due to the pandemic, and in 2021, the percentage of all four segments began to gradually increase, with the exception of the titanium waste and scrap market.

Fig. 3: Dynamics of average annual global titanium import 2003-2021, 2003 = 100 %

Source: calculated by me based on information: www.trademap.org

3.1.3 Major importers of different titanium products

Top 2 importers of titanium oxides are Germany and USA. The imports of either above country almost doubles the next country. Figure 4 shows the 12 main importing countries of titanium oxides, as well as their imported values in 2022 in US dollar thousand. The largest importers of titanium oxides were Germany (\$106412 thousand), the United States (\$102681 thousand), Belgium (\$52123 thousand), Spain (\$51031 thousand), Canada (\$49226 thousand) and so on.

Fig. 4: Importers of titanium oxides (2022) in US Dollar thousand

Source: www.trademap.org

China is the largest titanium ores imported country. Figure 5 shows the 12 main importing countries of titanium ores and concentrates, as well as their imported values in 2022 in US dollar thousand. As shown in the table, the largest importers of titanium concentrates were China (\$1397061 thousand), the United States (\$509117 thousand), Japan (\$446268 thousand), Belgium (\$3358818 thousand), Germany (\$270670 thousand) and etc. This table certainly shows

that China is the largest importer of ores concentrates, which is explained by large industrial enterprises, factories and the paint and varnish production, and so on.

Fig. 5: Importers of titanium ores and concentrates (2022) in US Dollar thousand

Source: www.trademap.org

Figure 6 shows the 12 main importing countries of titanium waste and their imported values in 2022 in US dollar thousand. The largest importers of titanium waste and scrap were the United States (\$785,924 thousand), France (\$695,468 thousand), China (\$680,492 thousand), Germany (\$598,214 thousand), United Kingdom (\$450,276 thousand) and so on.

Fig. 6: Importers of titanium waste and scrap (2022) in US Dollar thousand

Source: www.trademap.org

India is the largest country in the titanium pigments and preparations imports. As for the import of pigments and preparations based on TiO₂, the 12 main importing countries and their imported values in 2021 (US dollar thousand) can be viewed in Figure 7. The largest importers of pigments and preparations based on TiO₂ were India (\$1,014,255 thousand), Belgium (\$774,359 thousand), Germany (\$694,467 thousand), China (\$622,345 thousand), the United States

(\$593741 thousand) and so on. In this market segment, India is the leader with its growing industrial and construction production.

Fig. 7: Importers of pigments and preparations based on TiO2 (2021) in US Dollar thousand

Source: www.trademap.org

Netherlands imports the most of ferro-titanium and ferro-silico-titanium. It is also necessary to mention such a market segment as ferro-titanium and ferro-silico-titanium, despite the fact that this market is not as large as titanium concentrates or oxides. Figure 8 shows the 12 main importing countries of ferro-titanium and ferro-silico-titanium and their imported values in 2022 in US dollar thousand. The largest importers of this market segment were the Netherlands (\$61225 thousand), Germany (\$55115 thousand), Japan (\$49273 thousand), Korea (\$29849 thousand), France (\$23832 thousand) and etc.

Fig. 8: Importers of ferro-titanium and ferro-silico-titanium (2022) in US Dollar thousand

Source: www.trademap.org

3.2 Titanium Export

3.2.1 USA, China and Japan are the largest exporters of titanium

According to the Observatory of Economic Complexity (OEC), “in 2021 the top exporters of Titanium were United States, China, Japan, Germany, and Russia” (view in the Figure 9). “Between 2020 and 2021, the exports of Titanium grew the fastest in China (\$109M), Japan (\$41.6M), Germany (\$41.5M), Kazakhstan (\$30.3M), and South Korea (\$14.1M)”. Top 6 countries export 84% of the global titanium products. Since the total amount of titanium exports is \$4.51B, respectively, 23.7% of titanium exports are accounted for by America, 13% by China, 11.7% by Japan, 8.77% by Germany, 8.11% by Russia (Figure3).

Fig. 9: Exporters of titanium (2021) (millions of US Dollars)

Source: Observatory of Economic Complexity (OEC), 2021

Fig. 10: Titanium Exporters (2021) by percentage %

Source: calculated by me based on information: Observatory of Economic Complexity (OEC), 2021

3.2.2 Titanium exports do not vary greatly except titanium ores

Having considered the global titanium export by countries, it is necessary to distribute the titanium export into specific categories. Figure 11 shows the dynamics of global titanium exports from 2003 to 2021. The initial data for calculations are Trade Map data on the world value of titanium and its products exports from 2003 to 2021. The data is presented as a percentage of the level of the base year 2003 and calculated by me. Looking at the figure, we can see that the titanium market is divided into five main categories such as Titanium oxides, Titanium ores and concentrates, Titanium waste and scrap, Pigments and preparations based on TiO₂, Ferro-titanium and ferro-silico-titanium. Based on my calculations, it can be seen that the most unstable indicators are the export of Ferrotitane and ferrosilicate titanium, especially in the period 2003-2011 with a sharp jump from 2004 to 2005 and a sharp decline after 2005 to 2009. As well as imports, exports of titanium oxides/ pigments and preparations based on TiO₂ tend to develop more steadily, while exports of titanium waste and scrap tend to develop more smoothly, as for the segment of titanium ores and concentrates, its export values have a sharp increase in 2012 and a decline after 2012 to 2016. The export of oxides reached its maximum values in 2011, ores and concentrates export in 2012, waste and scrap export in 2019, the export of pigments in 2021, the export of ferro-titanium and ferro-silico-titanium in 2005. Again, the general pattern of all segments of the titanium export market is that the percentage of all exported products fell in 2020 due to the pandemic, and in 2021 the percentage of all four segments began to gradually increase, with the exception of the waste and scrap market.

Let's look at the main exporters of titanium products, because it is necessary to understand which countries have the largest production capacities for the extraction and processing of titanium.

Fig. 11: Dynamics of average annual global titanium export 2003-2021, 2003 = 100 %

Source: calculated by me based on information: www.trademap.org

3.2.3 China is the largest titanium oxides export country

Figure 12 shows the 12 main exporting countries of titanium oxides, as well as their exported value in 2022 in US dollar thousand. As can be seen from the table, the top exporters of titanium oxides were China (\$154292 thousand), Germany (\$130823 thousand), France (\$83918 thousand), Japan (\$78182 thousand), Korea (\$60892 thousand), other countries are listed in the table below.

Fig. 12: Exporters of titanium oxides (2022) in US Dollar thousand

Source: www.trademap.org

South Africa exports the most of titanium ores and concentrates in the world. The 12 main exporting countries and their exported values in 2022 (US dollar thousand) can be viewed in Figure 13. The largest exporters of ores and concentrates were South Africa (\$598604 thousand), Mozambique (\$470517 thousand), Senegal (\$185002 thousand), Belgium (\$180219 thousand), Madagascar (\$134571 thousand) and so on.

Fig. 13: Exporters of titanium ores and concentrates (2022) in US Dollar thousand

Source: www.trademap.org

USA exports the most of titanium waste and scrap in the world. Figure 14 shows the 12 main exporting countries of titanium waste and scrap, as well as the value of their exported values in 2022 in US dollar thousand. As shown in the table, the top exporters of titanium waste were the United States (\$1460061 thousand), China (\$798467 thousand), Japan (\$652724 thousand), United Kingdom (\$527056 thousand), Germany (\$491004 thousand), etc. At this stage, it is possible to notice a pattern that manufacturers of a large amount of titanium are also its consumers, such as the USA, China, United Kingdom and Germany.

Fig. 14: Exporters of titanium waste and scrap (2022) in US Dollar thousand

Source: www.trademap.org

China exports the most of titanium pigments and preparations. As for Figure 15, it shows the 12 main exporting countries of pigments and preparations based on TiO₂ and their exported values in 2022 in US dollar thousand. The top exporters of this category were China (\$3836010 thousand), the United States (\$1240996 thousand), Belgium (\$1240521 thousand), Germany (\$893889 thousand), Australia (\$604978 thousand) and etc.

Fig. 15: Exporters of pigments and preparations based on TiO₂ (2022) in US Dollar thousand

Source: www.trademap.org

Russian Federation export the most of ferro-titanium and ferro-silico-titanium. Figure 16 shows the 12 top exporting countries of ferro-titanium and ferro-silico-titanium and their exported values in 2021 in US dollar thousand. The largest exporters of this market segment were Russia (\$75356 thousand), United Kingdom (\$69512 thousand), Netherlands (\$42518 thousand), Germany (\$23077 thousand), Ukraine (\$20865 thousand) and other countries are listed in the table below. In comparison with other market categories, this segment is the smallest in the exported products value.

Fig. 16: Exporters of ferro-titanium and ferro-silico-titanium (2021) in US Dollar thousand

Source: www.trademap.org

3.3 Analysis of Price Dynamics

The analysis of the dynamics of prices for titanium is somewhat difficult compared, for example, with the main non-ferrous metals (aluminum, copper, tin, lead, zinc, nickel), which are exchange commodities, and the price of which is set on the London Metal Exchange (LME). Unlike these metals, there is no single world price for titanium, and prices in different countries may vary significantly.

The factors that can influence the price of titanium are supply and demand, the price of raw materials, the prices of titanium substitute metals. Let us consider the titanium market, for which there is available information until 2022, as well as information for 2021-2022 on the import and export of titanium products to the USA (Table 1).

For a more accurate price dynamic analysis of titanium products, I have divided titanium into three main production categories: titanium oxides, titanium ores and concentrates and titanium waste and scrap. In addition, I have created graphs according not only to the product specifics, but also used data corresponding to the three main exporting countries in these categories.

3.3.1 The unit price comparison of titanium oxides exports

The unit price of titanium exports by France ranks the highest, Germany follows, China is the lowest in the three countries. Figure 17 shows the change dynamics of exported unit value of titanium oxides in China, Germany and France, since these countries are the main exporters of titanium oxides. Prices for titanium oxides – export prices from 2003 to 2022 (exported unit value, US dollar/ton). As we can see, the titanium oxides price is unstable, there are undulating jumps in the growth and decline of prices. However, compared with 2003, the price of oxides in China has increased more than three times (from \$798 to \$2483 per ton) in 2022, moreover, the cost of Chinese titanium oxide is significantly lower than the cost of European titanium (Germany, France). The price in Germany has almost doubled (from \$2291 to \$4576 per ton), in France by 1.96 times (from \$2036 to \$3992 per ton) in 2022. It is important to note that prices in China and Germany in 2022 are the highest values since 2003. The graph also shows a drop in prices in 2020, but it is not as significant as, for example, in 2016. Despite a slight decline during Covid-19, a sharp increase in the price of titanium oxides in China and Germany in 2022, and in France in 2021 is clearly visible. As for France in 2022, a sharp decline in prices is noticeable, which is quite obvious, since 2022 turned out to be a difficult year for the European Union and the development of industry due to resource supply delays and so on.

Fig. 17: Change dynamics of exported unit value of titanium oxides in the main exporting countries, 2003-2022, in US Dollar/Tons

Source: www.trademap.org

3.3.2 The exported unit price of titanium ores and concentrates

Figure 18 shows the dynamics of changes in the unit value of exported titanium ores and concentrates in South Africa, Mozambique and Senegal, these countries are the main exporters of this production segment. Titanium ores and concentrates prices are export prices from 2014 to 2022, since information up to 2014 for some of these countries is not indicated (the value of the exported unit, US dollar/ton). Prices in all these countries in 2022 are the highest values since 2014. Moreover, the figure shows that prices for titanium ores and concentrates in all countries shown are quite stable, even the price equalization in Senegal and Mozambique from 2017 to 2021 is noticeable. However, there is a sharp increase in the cost in Senegal in 2022, as well as a slight increase in the price in South Africa and Mozambique. Most likely, this is caused by an increase in industrial production worldwide after the pandemic.

Fig. 18: Change dynamics of exported unit value of titanium ores and concentrates in the main exporting countries, 2014-2022, in US Dollar/Tons

Source: www.trademap.org

3.3.3 Unit price changes of exported titanium waste and scrap

Figure 19 shows the dynamics of changes in the unit value of exported titanium waste and scrap in the USA, China and Japan. Titanium waste and scrap prices are export prices from 2004 to 2022, since there is no information in the USA in 2003 (the value of the exported unit, US dollar/ton). As it can be seen in the figure, titanium waste and scrap price in the USA is abrupt, the sharpest jump occurred in 2006. Compared to 2004, the price in the United States increased by more than 2.4 times in 2022 and reached its maximum. Moreover, the price of American titanium waste and scrap is significantly higher than the price in China and Japan. Chinese titanium waste and scrap from 2004 to 2012 were unstable, there were price jumps, and in 2006 the price reached its maximum compared to 2004 to 2022. As for Japan, the price reached its maximum in 2008, after which it gradually began to decline. Price value in all countries is very different, American turned out to be the most expensive, while Japanese became the cheapest.

Fig. 19: Change dynamics of exported unit value of titanium waste and scrap in the main exporting countries, 2004-2022, in US Dollar/Tons

Source: www.trademap.org

3.3.4 The export price changes of titanium products

The analysis of price dynamics of titanium sponge, titanium dioxide, ilmenite and rutile in recent years shows the following trends (Table 1):

1. In 2022, in the fourth quarter, the price of titanium sponge (titanium metal) was about 11.40 US dollars per kilogram (the price of imported titanium from Japan). In the period from 2021 to 2022, prices for titanium sponge were fairly stable and amounted to about 10.70-11.70 US dollars per kilogram.
2. In 2022, in the fourth quarter, the price of titanium dioxide (pigment) it was 3.560 US dollars per kilogram (import price in the USA). In the period from 2021 to 2022, prices for titanium dioxide ranged from 2.740 to 3.600 US dollars per kilogram.
3. In 2022, in the fourth quarter, the price of ilmenite (concentrate) changed from 350 to 470 US dollars per ton (China). In the period from 2021 to 2022, ilmenite prices ranged from 260 to 470 US dollars per ton.
4. In 2022, in the fourth quarter, the price of rutile (concentrate) It was about 2000 US dollars per ton (Australia). In the period from 2021 to 2022, rutile prices ranged from 1200 to 2400 US dollars per ton.

	Q1 2021	Q2 2021	Q3 2021	Q4 2021	Q1 2022	Q2 2022	Q3 2022	Q4 2022
Concentrate:								
Ilmenite, CIF, China,	260-270	280-290	290-310	360-400	360-400	410-470	380-470	350-470
Titanium slag, import								
Canada	1,100	1,200	1,020	870	950	NA	1,030	NA
Norway	NA	730	800	780	NA	870	1,060	NA
South Africa	510	540	780	790	760	810	740	910
Rutile, natural:								
Bagged, f.o.b. Australian ports	1,300-1,400	1,400-1,500	1,450-1,500	1,450-1,550	1,700-2,000	2,200-2,300	2,000-2,400	2,000-2,400
Bulk, f.o.b. Australian ports	1,200-1,300	1,350-1,450	1,350-1,450	1,400-1,500	1,400-1,500	1,450-1,500	1,450-1,500	1,450-1,550
Metal:								
Sponge metal, Japan, import, dollars per kilogram	11.10	11.70	11.50	11.60	10.90	10.70	11.60	11.40
Titanium mill products producer price index	168	168	169	171	178	183	197	198
Titanium scrap, turnings, unprocessed (Ti-6Al-4V) dollars per pound	1.50-1.90	1.50-1.90	1.50-1.90	1.50-1.90	3.00-3.50	3.00-3.50	3.00-3.40	2.00-2.50
Ferrotitanium, 70% (max. 4.5% Al) per pound Ti	4.00-4.30	4.00-4.30	4.00-4.30	4.00-4.30	7.00-8.00	7.00-8.00	8.00-9.00	3.00-3.20
Pigment:								
Titanium dioxide pigment, import, dollars per metric ton	2,740	2,890	3,030	3,240	3,390	3,430	3,600	3,560

Table 1: Prices of global titanium trade (Dollars per metric ton)

Source: Titanium. Historical Statistics for Mineral and Material Commodities in the United States. National Minerals Information Center.

The reasons for the change in prices for titanium sponge and titanium dioxide are related to various factors. One of them is the instability of the global economy and changes in market regulation. In addition, there are problems with production and supply, as well as competition between suppliers. Thus, the prices of titanium sponge, titanium dioxide, ilmenite and rutile fluctuate depending on market demand, and ilmenite and rutile are more expensive materials than titanium sponge and titanium dioxide.

3.4 The impact of the Covid-19 on the titanium market

Like most industries, the titanium and titanium products market has not been left without the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic. There are several aspects of influence concerning the target segmentation of the titanium market. Firstly, there is a decrease in demand for titanium sponge in the aerospace and defense industries. Due to the shutdown of the aerospace sector around the world, with the crisis of airlines and the reduction of passenger traffic, the demand for titanium products used in the production of aircraft and spacecraft has decreased. Secondly, since titanium is a very sanitary material used in medicine, the demand for medical products made of titanium increased during the pandemic. In addition, due to financial difficulties caused by the pandemic, some industries were switching to cheaper alternatives to titanium.

To analyze the impact of Covid-19 on titanium market, I took four titanium market segments and considered the import and export of global titanium products for 2019, 2020 and 2021. Figure 20 shows the changes in titanium market imports

in the period from 2019 to 2021 in US Dollar thousand. As you can see in 2020, at the height of the pandemic, absolutely all market segments suffered, imports decreased significantly, for example, titanium oxides import decreased by 1.14 times, titanium ores and concentrates import by 1.06 times, waste and scrap import by 1.36, and ferro-titanium and ferro-silico-titanium by 1.41 times. Looking at 2021, we can note a gradual recovery, all market segments have increased their performance even compared to 2019, except for titanium waste and scrap.

Fig. 20: Changes in titanium market imports in the period from 2019 to 2021 in US Dollar thousand

Source: calculated by me based on information: www.trademap.org

Figure 21 shows the changes in titanium market exports in the period from 2019 to 2021 in US Dollar thousand. It also shows that in 2020, all market segments underwent a decline, for example, titanium oxides export decreased by 1.17 times, titanium ores and concentrates export by 1.02 times, waste and scrap export by 1.41 times, and ferro-titanium and ferro-silico-titanium by 1.33 times. In 2021, all market segments began to recover, increasing their performance compared to 2019, again with the exception of titanium waste and scrap.

Based on the analysis of imports and exports in the period 2019-2021, we can pay attention to the decline in the production capacity of the titanium market due to the coronavirus pandemic. However, as we can see, the recovery phase has begun in 2021, and the market is gradually stabilizing. Of course, part of the titanium market- ferro-titanium and ferro-silico-titanium is in the stage of improvement, but has not yet reached the scale in 2019. As for the prices of titanium products after the pandemic, it has increased in all market segments except France and Japan. Despite rising prices, imports and exports are increasing. Growing market investments, the desire for innovation and scientific and technological progress certainly help the market to cover losses and, consequently, create opportunities for expansion, which are useful for the growth of the global market.

Fig. 21: Changes in titanium market exports in the period from 2019 to 2021 in US Dollar thousand
 Source: calculated by me based on information: www.trademap.org

In general, COVID-19 has significantly affected the target segments and indicators of the titanium market. If we talk about the long-term perspective, titanium-containing raw materials remain important materials. Furthermore, it will continue to develop in the future.

4. The challenges that global titanium trade faces

4.1 High trading cost

One of the main problems of the titanium trading is its high cost. Titanium is a rare and expensive metal that can only be used in special conditions. In addition, titanium sponge and pure titanium production is an expensive process that requires high costs for expensive components and electricity for processing concentrates. The titanium production requires specialized equipment and knowledge, which makes its production chain even more complex and expensive. Due to the difficulties of titanium production and processing, we can observe price increases for titanium and its products.

4.2 Limited availability of titanium

Another problem is the limited availability of titanium. Despite the fact that titanium is one of the most common metals on earth, its extraction is a time-consuming process. Most of the titanium reserves are located in several countries, such as Australia, Canada and South Africa. These countries control most of the production of titanium materials, which may lead to the decreasing in the metal availability for other countries.

4.3 Environmental safety of the titanium production

There is also a problem with the environmental safety of the titanium production. The process of extraction and production of titanium materials can lead to environmental pollution and negatively affect the health of humans and animals.

4.4 The influence of Covid-19

Finally, there are also two challenges for titanium development in 2023: the geopolitical one and the consequences of the pandemic. Covid-19 has affected the demand for aircraft, cars and paint coatings. The pandemic has also influenced on supply chains and the workforce. Since 2021, the market has been recovering, but its capacity is limited due to the

strengthening of the geopolitical factor. The geopolitical situation has undermined the active recovery of the global economy after the COVID-19 pandemic, at least in the short term. This situation led to a sharp rise in commodity prices and supply chain disruptions, which caused inflation of goods and services and affected many markets around the world.

5. Recommendations to cope with the challenges

To overcome the problems associated with the titanium trade, the following recommendations can be considered:

1. **Technology development:** The development of new technologies that will allow titanium to be produced more efficiently with a high level of processing that meets the needs of modern industries and with fewer negative environmental consequences can help provide more affordable and environmentally friendly titanium for the global market.
2. **Market development:** The development and expansion of the titanium products market, aimed at the use of products by new consumers, can help the global titanium market expand and become more sustainable.
3. **Strengthening Government support:** The opportunity to use government support mechanisms during crisis periods (financing of new developments, creation of strategic metals reserves, and so on).
4. **Cooperation and knowledge sharing:** Cooperation between countries and the exchange of knowledge and technology can help improve titanium production and reduce its cost, as well as provide greater access to the metal. In addition, the cooperation development between states can help introduce new technologies and production methods and expand the availability of titanium.
5. **Introduction of more efficient, economical and environmentally friendly titanium production processes.** The development and implementation of efficient and environmentally friendly methods of titanium production can reduce the cost of the metal and increase its availability.
6. **Employee training and development.** A clear understanding of titanium production processes and technologies can help improve production efficiency and improve product quality. Training and staff development can help improve the knowledge and skills of employees, as well as correcting mistakes and preventing potential problems.
7. **Improving the supply management system.** Improving the supply management system can help improve the efficiency and accuracy of deliveries, reduce the risks of losses and ensure the correct distribution of metal.

6. Conclusion

According to the dynamic analysis of global titanium trade, it was investigated the market distribution, the main importers and exporters, price dynamics, the influence of external factors such as Covid-19 and geopolitical factor. Based on the research results, it can be concluded that market volatility is associated with a large industry differentiation. In Europe and North America, the aerospace industry regularly accounts for more than 60% of titanium demand. The production of titanium sponge and titanium products in these regions is also largely focused on the aerospace market. In addition, the rapid growth of titanium production in China is a consequence of the domestic demand growth in the industrial sector of the country.

Another conclusion is the use of titanium for industrial needs is more price-sensitive than in the case of the aerospace industry, and there is also strong competition from other metals and alloys manufacturers. This price sensitivity is more evident in Europe and North America than in China, which currently accounts for half of all industrial demand in the world. Based on calculations, it can be understood that the titanium using is preferable and cheaper to use in Chinese industrial factories compared to other materials. Moreover, titanium production for space technologies is mainly produced in Japan, Russia, the USA and Kazakhstan. And in addition, imports to the United States account for more than

half of the world titanium sponge trade and American companies are heavily dependent on imports from Japan and Kazakhstan.

Despite all the threats and challenges, price increases in almost all titanium market segments, political and social factors, the titanium industry is developing, trade is increasing, and sales and supplies are growing. In my opinion, all these actions are proof that titanium is an indispensable material for not only innovation and technology development, but also the household industry. Besides that, IT industry and Artificial Intelligence are part of our new reality, but without an industrial base and materials such as titanium, the development of these technology is not feasible.

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